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CONTEXTS OF EXPERIENCE (COE)
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A PSYCHOLOGY-BASED DESIGN TOOL, TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION THROUGH EXTENDING THE PRODUCT LIFETIME

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ABSTRACT

This article introduces how one can design for product longevity through eliciting consumer-product attachment in order to restrain the rate of product replacement. The research disclosed the design tool "Contexts of Experience" (COE) which combines strategies of consumer-product attachment and associated psychological phenomenon. The COE was disclosed and analyzed through case study.

Keywords: sustainable consumption, product lifetime optimization, sustainable behavior

EXTENDED LIFETIME

People's pattern of consumption is often related to feelings. High quality products working according to functional needs are replaced out of emotional sentiments such as self expression, convenience, status and belonging. Such premature replacement is unfavorable for the environment (Chapman, 2005; Nicole van Nes, 2006). Extending the lifetime of products reduce the impact on the environment through a lower rate of product replacement causing cutbacks in manufacturing and consequently less use of resources such as energy, transport and land. One promising strategy to extend the life time of a product is to increase a person's feeling of attachment towards a product throughout the whole period of an ownership. However it is a complex task to turn the strategies of consumer-product attachment into design parameters and finally a product that evokes feelings of attachment. The constitution of the strategies of consumer-product

attachment, awareness of stages of ownership and the associated psychological phenomenon of habits and persuasion are make the basis of the design tool COE to achieve CPA.

Nes & Cramer (2005) has defined product lifetime as the duration of the life of a product starting from acquisition (new or second hand) and ending at the moment of replacement. We recognize that targeting the experiences of all stages of an ownership in the design process (see Discussion/"Product ownership - contexts of experience") is an important factor regarding the lifetime of products. Consequently we suggest an extended version of Nes & Cramer's definition to include the pre-purchase and the late/post ownership of a product. We therefore define product lifetime as; the duration of the life of a product starting from the planning phase of possible acquisition or replacement of an existing product and ending with the planning of and finally the moment of replacement.

Based on the research question of; how one can design for extend product lifetime and the assumption that CPA can extend the lifetime of a product we formulated the assumptions that made the premises for the COE.

CPA:

- can be triggered by product, system and market functions of based on awareness of persuasion psychology
- is more likely to be obtained if the designer creates contexts in which the product is experienced with the purpose to change and establish consumer habits and behavior

- can be strengthened by designing for specific experiences for different stages of an ownership

Reasons for replacement

Products are purchased partly out of the desire of feeling pleasure (Jordan, 2002). The joyful feeling evoked by owning a newly purchased product drains quickly and interest for new products therefore build up (Chapman, 2005; Dahlén & Kuipers, 2010). Dahlén & Kuipers (2010) found that people favor the taste of the water that is presented in the next generation packaging in comparison to the existing packaging, even though the same water is used in both situations. The dimension of being new can therefore be considered as a utility. The product that a person possesses is experienced as less attractive when the owner becomes aware of the advantages of a new product that overpower the utilities of the existing product (figure 1.). Nes & Cramer has developed a model that gives insight to motivations for replacement and therefore also partly insight into what makes a person hang on to a product (see figure 1.).

Figure 1. Model factors influencing the replacement decision by N. van Nes & J. Cramer.

Extended lifetime and commercial interests

Designers are today challenged by their clients to build an emotional value linked to the product they create in relation to commercial interests (Kapferer, 2008; Lindström, 2005; Næss & Blichfeldt, 1998; Samuelsen, Peretz, & Olsen, 2007).

The combination of commercial and sustainable gain through calming the replacement rate of products might be considered as incompatible. We assume however that a tool that enables designers to elicit consumer-product attachment (CPA) will be of relevance for companies by possible market gain by

increased consumer loyalty and activation as a result of the achieved CPA.

CONSUMER-PRODUCT ATTACHMENT

Schifferstein & Zwartdruis-Pelgrim define product attachment (PA) as: the degree of consumer-product attachment is the strength of the emotional bond a consumer experiences with a durable product (H. N. J. Schifferstein & Zwartkruis-Pelgrim, 2008). The feeling of attachment is furthermore described as the emotional tie to a specific durable product example separated from the linked product brand. We understand a durable product to be a product that utilizes the expected functions for a period over several years, in contrast to fast moving consumer goods. Examples of durable products can be lamps, chairs, watches and cars.

Kleine and Allens definition on product attachment give emphasis to the person's ability of self extension (Kleine, Kleine, & Allen, 1995). This emphasis excludes the use of some strategies for product attachment when designing for experiences through e.g. more general psychological principles that have to do with behavior apart from self extension.

Perception of a product relies on the context in which the physical item is experienced or perceived (Cialdini, 2009; Grankvist & Biel, 2007). The potential of influencing a customer or user is therefore greater when creating the product and context and or brand as a whole (Hestad, 2008). Brand developers often analyze product uniqueness by describing its utilities as facets of a personality when creating a brand essence (Næss & Blichfeldt, 1998). The engendered personality descriptions are possible to include as influencing parameters in a design process. Hence by allowing the brand essence to have influence on the physical product the product might strengthen and sustain the brand through how the product is perceived. It is difficult to break down the different facets of product experiences from the total product experience. We therefore include the dimensions of brand, self extension and other possible psychology-based experiential factors as a part of the understanding of a product. We employed Schifferstein & Pelgrims definition for PA with the latter understanding of product for this study.

Strategies for consumer-product attachment (CPA)

We have disclosed several strategies for product attachment from design research in order to set the premises for the design tool COE:

- *Design more enjoyable products, Develop products that are used together with other people, Design products that gracefully accumulate the signs of their usage history in their appearance* (Hendrik N.J. Schifferstein & Zwartkruis-Pelgrim, 2008)
- *Subject object dependency, Reliance and need, Ability to alter, Inherent feedback, Create meaning* (Chapman, 2005)
- *Mastering complex products designed to evoke pride, Exploring the possibilities of multifunctional products designed to evoke joy,* (Hendrik N. J. Schifferstein & Desmet, 2010)
- *Product personalization, Memories, Self expression, Group affiliation,* (Mugge, Schoormans, & Schifferstein, 2009(Ball & Tasaki, 1992))
- *The development of products that can evolve with the changing desires of the consumer.* (Nicole van Nes, 2006)
- *Products recommend by a person with authority, Scarce products, products that are associated with inner consistency, products received from people you like* (Cialdini, 2009)

PSYCHOLOGICAL PHENOMENON

People's perception of a situation can be poles apart. As Steven R. Covey (Covey, 1990) put it:

Two people can see the same thing, disagree, and yet both can be right. It is not logical it is psychological.

S.R. Covey found that people in a group would disagree on if the portrait (picture 1.) pictures an old or a young woman. Furthermore when the people realized that they can in fact identify both women in the picture, it is almost impossible to see them at the same time.

The comprehension of perception as a part of a person's opinion of reality seems therefore favorable to be aware of for a designer, in order to elicit CPA through products.

In order for a designer to understand a broader picture of behavior and how to influence it, we suggest the inclusion of the awareness of psychological phenomenon when working with consumer product attachment. We assume that this

can enable designers to stage a context in which a product performs, more strategically and therefore influence perception and behavior.

Picture 1. Perceptual illusion (Covey, 1990)

HABITS

To change consumption patterns you have to change people's habits. People have the propensity to make decisions on grounds that originate in earlier behavior (Grankvist & Biel, 2007; Verplanken, Walker, Davis, & Jurasek, 2008). Consumption behavior is partly driven by a perceived balance of costs and benefits (Ajzen, 1991; Verplanken, et al., 2008) but it is also driven by repeated behavior. K. Lewin described habits as; "behavior performed without considering the relations to own attitudes" (Lewin, 1951). He used the term "frozen" for habitual behavior, the change of habits as "unfreezing" and finally the settling of a new behavior as "freezing".

The developing (freezing) of habits

Regular experience of rewarding consequences as a result of behavior is important for a habit to develop (Grankvist & Biel, 2007); furthermore the strength of a habit is reflected by the frequency of past behavior (Grankvist & Biel, 2007; Ouellette & Wood, 1998; Verplanken, et al., 2008). Stability in the context of behavior is also a significant factor for a habit to develop (Grankvist & Biel, 2007).

Changing behavior- Unfreezing habits

In order to break habits Dahlstrand & Biel (1997) has proposed 7 sub-steps to Lewins 3 steps of behavioral change in their work on pro-environmental consumption namely: 1. Activation, 2. Attending present behavior 3. Consider alternative solution 4. Planning new behavior, 5. Testing new behavior 6. Evaluation of new behavior 7. Establishment of new habit. The three first stages describe a method on how to change or unfreeze habits.

The stage of activation or “priming” demonstrates how people are more likely to consider alternative behavior through the intervention of the behavioral or cognitive pattern. Such activation can be done by active communication of values through e.g. prompted questions related to a forthcoming experience (Grankvist & Biel, 2007). Activating a person just by asking a about attitudes towards eco-labeled products leads to increased purchase of eco-labeled products (Grankvist & Biel, 2007) regardless of a persons attitude. Influence psychology also show that in a context where a person is open for an assortment of behaviors the prompting of information about what *others do* in equivalent situations, will lead to the consideration of behavior along with what the *others do* , particularly if they are recognized to be in majority or with authority (Cialdini, 2009). Dahlstrand & Biel found that activation has to be linked to the step of attending present behavior otherwise the person will behave in accordance with its habit.

To consider alternative solutions people need to know the outcome of the new behavior. Dahlstrand & Biel gives the following example of such a situation:

a person has to know where batteries can be returned not only that they can be returned before considering present behavior and planning new behavior (Dahlstrand & Biel, 1997).

Habit contexts

Stable contexts of habitual stimuli are likely to exert an influence on behavior, the factors making the context can be physical or perceptual, social and cognitive (Grankvist & Biel, 2007; Verplanken, et al., 2008). Verplanken 2008 defines a context as the environment where a behavior takes place. The design process often imply the creation of experiences prior to behavior (ref. contrast phenomenon) we therefore define context as; environment where an experience or a behavior

takes place. Contexts that are new or experienced difficult or unstable for a person will strengthen the role of intention as an influence on behavior, rather than habits.

Values and habits

Attitudes together with a subjective norm and perceived behavioral control influence behavior (Ajzen, 1987; Grankvist & Biel, 2007; Verplanken, et al., 2008) even though the expression of an intention is often guided by the salience of past behavior rather than by attitudes (Cialdini, 2009; Dahlstrand & Biel, 1997; Grankvist & Biel, 2007; Verplanken, et al., 2008) found that the considering of the purchase of eco-labeled products is influenced through new attitudes towards the environment only when the new attitude can be associated with the old behavior (Grankvist & Biel, 2007). Cialdini found that the degree of propensity to behave as *others do* (social proof) relate to own attitude or value (inner consistency)(Cialdini, 2009). When for example a product is presented along with a set of pro-environmental values to a person holding these values, it is more likely that the product will be considered positive. Generally there is a gap between a person’s pro-environmental attitude and actual behavior. In fact Verplanken et al. (2008) found that the people with a high environmental concern does not make different choices than those with a low environmental concern in relation to the choice of transport utilities unless they are cognitively activated. If people’s pro-environmental values are activated however they have the propensity to act according to their value.

PERSUASION PSYCHOLOGY

Persuasion principles can be understood as cognitive shortcuts that release a person to consider behavior in a certain context. Shortcuts are useful when important choices have to be made in an instant of time. An example of such a situation: parts of a group notice an attacker approaching and starts escaping; others within the group that has not yet seen the attacker escapes too because they notice others that are running away. Doing what others do (social proof (Cialdini, 2009)) in this example is in fact important to survive.

In the information age of today cognitive shortcuts may come in handy e.g. in order to know what kind of proposals to steer away from or to react positive towards.

Fogg, B. J. (2003) has defined persuasion as an attempt to change attitudes or behaviors or both without using coercion or deception involving voluntarily change (Fogg, 2003).

Persuasion principles:

Reciprocation (R) - When people receive something positive such as a gift, favor, attention, compliment etc., they feel obliged to give something back, ex, bringing flowers to a dinner party (Cialdini, 2009).

Commitment and Consistency (CC)- Commitments made especially in writing makes you more persistent to keep you promise (Cialdini, 2009). The more work you put into an experienced obligation - the stronger the feeling of obligation (Moestue, 2009). Example: In Oslo 7% of all partners with common children split up annually while the ratio of all marriages in Oslo ending in divorce is 1.45% annually (SSB, 2003).

Social Proof (SP) - Similar to *Principle of Recognition*, Fogg (2006). People decide what is appropriate for them to do in a situation by examining what others are doing (Cialdini, 2009). The *Principle of Competition - Social comparison*, shows similar mechanisms; people have the propensity to perform a targeted behavior when they can compare their own performance with others individuals, especially persons that compare with themselves (Fogg, 2006) p. 194.

Authority (A) - Similar to *Principle of Trustworthiness or Credibility*, Fogg (2006). People tend to obey authority figures, even if they are asked to perform against their own will (S. Milgram, 1969). Signs and symbols convey information of authority such as uniforms and medals.

Liking (L) - Similar to *principle of Cooperation and similarity*, Fogg (2006). People are easily persuaded by people they like or are alike. Cooperation and similarities triggers the feeling of liking. Tupperware (multi level marketing) is a typical context of influence where one person is selling products to friends and family.

Scarcity (S) - Perceived scarcity will generate demand. Example: increased value because of less availability such as antiques and gold.

Contrast phenomenon: In addition to the principles of persuasion Cialdini describes the “contrast phenomenon” as a basis for an experience. The contrast phenomenon illustrates the change of people’s perception through what they have just perceived, for instance in a bargaining situation. Another example: if you put a finger into hot water followed by lukewarm water the perception of the lukewarm water will be that it is cold. Another example illustrates how we are influenced by what we perceive prior to a situation is: a man that is talking to a very attractive woman at a party is joined by a less attractive woman, the latter person will then be perceived as less attractive than in another context. The example of the perception of the women in picture 1 is also be explained by the contrast principle.

Principle of Convenience (web based): People are more easily persuaded through experiences that are experienced as easy to access. (Fogg, 2003) Some of these principles are complex to implement as a function in a product or product system while others can implemented in a very practical manner during the design phase. Cialdinis principle of scarcity can for example be elicited through producing fewer products than the marked desires (Gulden, Moestue, & Berg, 2010). Such a situation will evoke feelings of craving by the ones that cannot obtain the product and possibly more valuable by the ones that own one. Products that are made specially tailored for or by one person is an illustration of such a situation.

METHOD

Design strategies of product attachment and psychological phenomenon are proposed as enabling factors in the COE to design for product longevity. We therefore set up a collaborating team that combined competence of influence & behavior psychology and design. Literature study of product longevity and sustainable issues, product attachment strategies, branding and behavior & habit psychology disclosed the key terms in the “Contexts of Experience” (COE) (Jørgensen, 1992).

Furthermore the COE made the basis for a case study with our first year master students in product design to analyze the COE in diverse contexts. The students were introduced to the COE and related theory by a designer/ design researcher and a psychologist. Concept mapping was performed on student reports and unstructured interviews made with the students. The form was chosen because it was assumed apt to produce useful data from the different students with experiences from a wide-range of design focus within the use of COE. Main issues that made the questions in the interviews were; experiences of working with the COE, how the COE influenced their working process and final product concept, suggested changes for the COE, if the COE would influence their future work.

The students also performed interviews and questionnaires in order to collect data about people's behavior in relation to products.

DISCUSSION

Sustainable design, stages of product life

It is widely recognized from a sustainable design approach that it is an imperative to determine how to design for all stages of a product life (Jakobsen, 1997; McDonough & Braungart, 2008; Tischner, 2000). UNEPS design guide for sustainable design (Dr. M.R.M. Crul 2006) involves the consideration of environmental impact of all phases of a product creation and use, such as the extraction of material, processing of raw materials, product manufacturing, distribution, use, reuse and disposal. This life cycle thinking is mostly concerned with technical sides of a products life with little emphasis on the dimension of consumption patterns. In most situations a reduced replacement rate of life cycle considered products will cause less impact on the environment. It is in some cases environmentally sound to replace a product if the existing product uses a considerable amount of energy, chemicals etc. in the use phase compared to the new product.

CONTEXTS OF EXPERIENCE A DESIGN TOOL

"Design tool" in this context is understood as a technique that facilitates the designer in defining design parameters based on knowledge engendered through working with the COE. The COE should of

course be used in addition with other tools and methods in order to fulfill other design goals. This tool is meant as a non hierarchic design process. The numbering of the different contexts is based on a possible sequence of a product experience in relation to influence and not the working sequence.

The construct of Contexts of Experience

The knowledge of the "relative advantage" proposed by Nes & Cramer (see figure 1.) illustrates the need for designers to know how to influence and change consumer behavior in the different stages of an ownership in relation to time and product experience.

Ball and Tasaki (Ball & Tasaki, 1992) distinguishes between five stages in an ownership in relation to product attachment: preacquisition, early ownership, mature ownership, predisposal, and post disposal. These stages represent different contexts where products are experienced differently throughout the ownership.

We defined the following contexts of experience throughout a product lifetime to be;

1. Pre-purchase, 2. Point of purchase (POP), 3. Product, 4. Product use and 5. Late use/ planning of replacement/post use.

The context of experience at point of purchase is an added dimension to Ball and Tasakis stages of ownership. This is suggested since this context is of vital importance to design for in order to influence people to consider new behavior. Point of purchase- a term well known in marketing departments might support the consideration of designing for product longevity since it conveys purposes for financial as well as sustainable gain. The disclosed term Pre-POP is synonymous with Ball and Tasakis pre-acquisition stage but it is renamed in order to be link up with the POP stage and to meet market values.

Ball and Tasakis stages of pre and post disposal are combined in the one context of *late use/ planning of replacement/post use*. The *planning of replacement* comes as an additional dimension in order to enable the process of linking the late and post use experience to the Pre-Purchase stage in relation to market and sustainable reasons (assuming that the manufacturer that uses the COE have products with less environmental impact than its competitors).

The stage of Product experience is included as a phase of ownership since it embodies the typical core competence of designers, namely to transform the influencing strategies of PCA into perception and experience.

Context of experience 1. Pre-purchase.

Habit psychology shows that it is important to activate a person in order for the person to consider a change of behavior. Costly durable products can lead to a longer phase of planning the purchase due to people’s need of saving up for the purchase. Fantasizing about how it will be to have a product is likely to strengthen the degree of product attachment also after the product has been purchased (H. N. J. Schifferstein & Zwartkruis-Pelgrim, 2008). This planning phase makes a possible space to design a possible customer experience prior to the purchase experience. Design research, persuasion psychology and brand theory also show that brand loyalty and the feeling of product attachment is strengthened through time and effort spent in the planning of a purchase and use (Cialdini, 2009; Samuelsen, et al., 2007). We identify this activation phase that comes prior

to the experience at point of purchase as: *Context of experience 1. Pre-purchase.*

Context of experience 2. Point of Purchase (POP).

Staging the context of purchase the experience provides the potential to influence people to attend habitual behavior and consider alternative solutions after being activated in the Pre-purchase phase. The often limited time and confined experience at POP influence the customer to perceive a product in comparison with other products or other factors of influence. The comparison that influence the thinking prior to the choice made at POP is often perceived as rational. Remote to the shopping experience however the choice might be experienced differently. An example of such a context of comparison: The most expensive object out of e.g. three is perceived too costly and the cheapest not good enough. The range of prizes can in other words influence the perception of quality (see contrast phenomenon) (Cialdini, 2009). It is the comparison that influences the perception- a comparison or “framing” possible for designers to stage.

The designing of a context in which a product is

Figure 2. Context of experience by Tore Gulden

experienced is identified as: *Context of experience 2. Point of Purchase.*

Context of experience 3. Product

The bodily geometry and semantic properties elicit experiences by the users' cognitive processes and feelings through for example associations, recognition and habits, factors known to influence feelings for a product (Chandon, 2002; Warell, 2008). Knowledge of relevant psychological phenomenon can help the designer with strategies to elicit specific feelings by the owner such as; being special through having something scarce, belonging to a specific social or cultural position, expressing values etc.

A persons desire to express one's self can be feelings elicited in this context (Ball & Tasaki, 1992; Schifferstein & Zwartkuis-Pelgrim, 2008).

We identify the context of experience brought forth by the product appearance as the: *Context of experience 3. Product.*

Context of experience 4. Use

The degree of habit strength is determined by the frequency of past behavior. A designed context of use can for example enable repeated action to upgrade a product with new software and hardware during an ownership. Such a possibility can lead to the testing of new behavior through e.g. upgrading products. If such an upgrade can lead to a desired level of technical and emotional experience, rather than to feelings of desires for new products that overpower the utilities of the existing product, the new behavior might establish.

A product might also involve activating interaction with other people that creates situations of liking (Cialdini, 2009) such as social touch points inspired by (Putnam, 2001) or activities that resemble with the interest of the user. Activities facilitated through product use might elicit the desire to keep the product out of emotional sentiments by memories and habits gained through history with the product. We identify the context of experience brought forth by use as the: *Context of experience 4. Use*

Context of experience 5. Late use/ planning of replacement/post use.

Awareness of the planning process related to thoughts of replacement that begins at this phase, can reveal potential functions for the design of the experience that a person with established habits, meets in the possible Pre-purchase phase. A designer can design for situations where an owner makes plans for how to get rid of a product or parts of a product. A product can be passed on to others, turned in for recycling etc. Such actions can e.g. be linked up to the Pre-Purchase phase.

We identify the context of experience brought forth in the late phase of ownership as the: *Context of experience 5. Late use/ post use/planning of replacement.*

Habits and working with COE

In stable contexts habits are likely to develop and to exert an influence on behavior (Grankvist & Biel, 2007) we assume this to be true also for the ones performing creative processes as any other behavior. In order for the designer to influence people to break with their habitual consumption pattern, he or she needs to break with their own habitual process as well. An approach that enhances the designers' comprehension of this fact might result in constant changes in working contexts as an important part of a design process.

Product area

As mentioned- extended lifetime for products is not in all cases the optimal situation. Thus it is important to evaluate the possible sustainable gain through extended lifetime for each product area. For this study we have chosen typically durable products such as interior pieces, electronic products that last long because of good construction but often replaced out of emotionally sentiments.

We assume that findings from habit research are relevant for durable products even though this research is done in relation to the scope of travel modes and in relation to the purchase of fast moving consumer goods.

One of the main factors for a habit to form is the result of repeated behavior. It seems therefore reasonable to assume that it takes less effort to change habits related to the purchase of products

that are acquired less often such as more durable products like chairs, lamps, telephones etc.

Aesthetical factors as part of product attachment

When a product is replaced it is not necessarily discarded. A product that for one person is outdated out of aesthetical reasons can for another be perfect. Strategically products can be designed for extended lifetime in this perspective.

Comprehensive research is done to identify generic form grammar attractive to people such as: Ad Quadratum & divine proportions, rounded shapes, product appearance etc. (Blijlevens, Creusen, & Schoormans, 2009; Creusen & Schoormans, 2005; Lund, 1921; H. Schifferstein & Hekkert, 2008). These findings can be included in all product development to motivate products to be passed on rather than discarded. These aesthetically based factors are interesting for the Product context in order to evoke intended experiences. This study however does not go into describing such methods.

Ethical implications

The COE can of course be used solely with the intention to increase sales and earn financial gain. One should expect however that designers, with pro-environmental values will influence clients and companies to see the need of sustaining the environment. When designers can present a process that can lead to the win-win situation of consumers and manufacturer “cooperating” for the environment, the company might also see the potential of a gain of reputation.

PROJECTS AND FINAL REMARKS

In order to analyze the COE in diverse contexts, design students have worked with the COE in a design project. The students that were interviewed after the project was concluded pointed out that the COE facilitated them to look upon a product as something that can elicit different experiences rather than merely a tangible product piece. Especially the dimension of PRE-POP is mentioned by the students as a new dimension in their design process. Some of the core functions in the student projects have its roots in working with this stage of experience.

Project example, Spa radiator

One student chose to design for an active experience during the use phase of a radiator for home use (picture 2.). This thinking process led to discussions about heat in relation to pleasure as in situations of spa and relaxation. One of the ideas engendered from this process was to include stones that could hold heat for some time, as instruments for massage and relaxation. She tested out her ideas by presenting the experience with the stones alone to people, not mentioning the relation to the radiator function at first (picture 3.).

As a result of these tests the stones were introduced as part of the product concept.

The stones turned out to be a major dimension in the students planning of the experience for the contexts of Pre-Purchase and POP. Pre-purchase situations were suggested to activate and involve potential customers through prompting the possibility of: “bring nature home” through active marketing.

Picture 2. Spa radiator by Siri B. Persen

The concept suggests future customers to be activated not only in the planning of their own product but also to personalize the coming purchase by the collecting of stones of unique interest, perhaps by including family and friends in the act. If the customers have no collection of stones at home before the purchase situation, the concept includes the possibility to buy different stones with special shapes, materials and colors that the customers can choose between at POP (picture 4.).

Picture 3. Spa radiator, Testing experience, Siri B. Persen

Picture 4. Picking out favorites at POP, Siri B. Persen

Working with the experience dimension of a product

The student refers to the process of working with the COE as frustrating, though she states that she made it graspable and useful by making the COE process into her own.

She found the process of designing an experience prior to the product interesting and that it

represents a new design dimension for her. As she points out:

It was fun to focus on the experience part of a product in the design phase rather than tactile and material aspects of a product, it made me realize that a product is an experience and not only something pretty. I have made a product that elicit many and very different experiences such as: spiritual (I know spiritual people love stones), taking nature in to your home, Spa, esthetics, interaction and health.

Project example, Ski wax

This product example is a packaging concept for soft sticky ski wax for the company Swix. The student used the COE as part of her process. One of the strategies of CPA that she wanted to implement as a function in the concept was to design for joint use. By looking into the use phase of the existing product the student found that most people think of the packaging solution as messy to handle, so messy in fact that some of the people interviewed did not go skiing when the snow conditions required such wax. The student came up with the suggestion to pack the ski wax in small polymer bags, one bag for one ski. One package consists of two bags; this makes it possible to put the used bag into another in order to keep the packaging in a pocket for a later disposal. As a result of considering functions for the Pre-purchase phase of the product the student suggested that the packaging solution could be used as a give-away for activation (priming) purpose in order to trigger the feeling of reciprocity by the receiver, (Cialdini, 2009).

Picture 5. Portion packaging for ski wax, Margrete R. Nielsen

Figure 6. Swix packaging, Margrete R. Nielsen

The goal to create a packaging system based on joint ownership or use engendered an application (picture 6.) where smart phone users could exchange real time information about the perfect ski wax for the present snow conditions. The portion pack was also stimulated by the intention to inspire skiers to exchange ski wax with each other in the tracks, as a social function of the product. Both the Pre-purchase situation and the real time application were found to be very interesting by the company that the student cooperated with during the master exam.

Durable packaging

Some students worked with typically durable products. However a number of students looked into the possibility to turn fast moving consumer goods such as packaging, into durable products with refill systems etc. (picture 8.)

Picture 7. Detergent packaging for colored and white clothes with refill packaging. Kjersti Resell

Implication for designers & Further research

This case study is brought forth with the goal to improve designers' ability to design for product longevity. The COE is a design tool based on a constitution of theory that can enable designers to strengthen peoples felling of attachment in order to calm the rate of product replacement. The products developed by the students with support from the COE are designed according to some of the principles on how to persuade a customer to break purchase and use habits and finally get attached to the product. Spite this fact it is not possible to say if people are more likely to purchase or stick on to these products for a longer time before replacement. As the creator of the Spa Radiator says:

I do not believe that the experience functions induced in this radiator will postpone the product replacement by the user.

Even so, if trusting the empirical data that this tool builds upon, it seems it would be a missed opportunity not to use the COE- to extend the lifetime of products. Design partly based upon psychological phenomenon is a commonly unused possibility that the COE-tool makes possible. The COE enabled some of the design students to turn disposable packaging into durable products linked to a refill system in order to reduce packaging, change user behavior (by introducing half load tablets) , create new user experiences and enhance customer loyalty (picture 7.). The students commented that they found the COE to open up for the dimension of experience as a design parameter in general and furthermore that the Context1. Pre-Purchase was of particularly interest being a new dimension for them to target as designers. Further research on how to design for the Pre-POP stage might therefore bring to surface new and more detailed knowledge on how to design for this experience and what the effect of this experience might have in relation to the environmental impact.

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